

Ferrous-Phosphoric Acid Complex

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Experimental evidences obtained indicate the formation of a complex between ferrous ion and phosphoric acid. The thermodynamic stability constant of the complex has been determined from *pH*-titration. The values of *K* are $2.189 (\pm 0.22) \times 10^7$ at 30° and $1.06 (\pm 0.13) \times 10^7$ at 20° and ΔH and ΔS are $12.8 (\pm 2)$ kcal./mole and $75 (\pm 0)$ e.u. respectively.

Although the literature provides numerous evidence of complex formation between ferric ion and phosphoric acid, there is hardly any evidence of complexes of ferrous ion with phosphoric acid. Faucherre and Masiku¹ reported a weak complex between ferrous ion and phosphoric acid. Some evidences of the existence of the complex along with stability constant are reported in the present communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

$\text{Fe}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ was prepared by dissolving iron wire (A.R., Riedel) in about 0.5-0.7 *M*- HClO_4 and was kept in an atmosphere of nitrogen. $\text{Fe}(\text{ClO}_4)_3$ was prepared by oxidising $\text{Fe}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ with H_2O_2 (G.R., E. Merck) and the excess H_2O_2 was decomposed.

Iron content of both the solutions was estimated with a standard potassium dichromate solution. NaOH (G.R., E. Merck) solution was standardised against a standard succinic acid (E. Merck, G.R.) using phenolphthalein as indicator. A solution of phosphoric acid was prepared from phosphoric acid (G.R., E. Merck) by dilution and standardised against standard NaOH , using bromocresol green as indicator. All other reagents were of E. Merck reagent grade. The solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

A Leeds-Northrup K_2 type potentiometer was used for the measurements of E.M.F. A normal calomel electrode was prepared by the method of Hill and Ives². The salt bridge and the electrode vessels were of the type used by Nath *et al*³.

The E. M. F. measurements of the cells of the type:

were taken. The concentrations of Fe^{3+} and H_3PO_4 were kept constant and that of Fe^{2+}

1. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1962, 1824.
2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 311.
3. *This Journal*, 1951, 28, 683.

was varied. For this cell, if the Fe^{2+} ion does not react with H_3PO_4 , the E.M.F. will be given by

$$E = E_0 - \frac{RT}{F} \ln a_{\text{Fe}^{2+}}.$$

The observed E.M.F. readings plotted against $\log(\text{Fe}^{2+})$ should have a slope of about -0.06 (slight deviation due to activity coefficient corrections). The experimental slope (-0.026) is much different from -0.06 , indicating that Fe^{2+} ion forms complexes with phosphoric acid.

The solutions for pH measurements were prepared by taking definite amounts of $\text{Fe}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and different amounts of H_3PO_4 and diluting to the mark. Blank solutions were prepared with the same amounts of phosphoric acid as in the previous solutions and with perchloric acid, equivalent to the amount of free acid in $\text{Fe}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ solution. pH measurements were taken with a Cambridge bench type pH-meter. Experiments were carried out at 20° and 30° ; at 30° two different ionic strengths were used. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Concentration $\times 10^2 M$, $\text{Fe}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$.	H_3PO_4 .	pH		Ionic strength.	$K_T/10^7$.	Average.
		$\text{Fe}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ $+\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4$.	Blank soln.			
Temp. = 30° .						
	1.0	1.90	2.04	0.1067	2.187	
	2.0	1.79	1.97	0.1067	2.402	
	3.0	1.72	1.98	0.1067	3.087	2.100
3.333	4.0	1.70	1.92	0.1067	2.336	(± 0.24)
	5.0	1.89	1.87	0.1067	1.536	
	6.0	1.69	1.88	0.1067	1.501	
	7.0	1.63	1.85	0.1067	1.658	
	2.0	1.92	2.10	0.064	2.251	
	3.0	1.84	2.03	0.064	1.588	
2.0	4.0	1.78	1.98	0.064	1.862	2.278
	5.0	1.72	1.96	0.064	2.646	(± 0.204)
	6.0	1.69	1.92	0.064	3.084	
	7.0	1.68	1.91	0.064	2.325	
	8.0	1.66	1.88	0.064	2.185	
Temp. = 20° .						
4.0	2.0	1.84	1.98	0.134	1.227	
4.0	4.0	1.80	1.92	0.134	0.602	
4.0	5.0	1.75	1.92	0.134	0.945	1.06
2.0	2.0	1.80	1.86	0.178	1.543	(± 0.13)
2.0	3.0	1.79	1.84	0.178	0.829	
2.0	4.0	1.76	1.85	0.178	1.392	
2.0	5.0	1.75	1.82	0.178	0.881	

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta S &= 75 (\pm 6) \text{ e.u.} \\ -\Delta H &= -12.8 (\pm 2) \text{ kcal./mole.} \end{aligned}$$

DISCUSSION

The pH of the solution containing Fe²⁺ ion was always lower than that of the blank. This indicates formation of complex with H₃PO₄. The calculation of the formation constant of the complex from the redox-concentration cell is dependent on that of ferric phosphate complex. So we have used only the pH readings for the evaluation of the stability constant.

Ferric ion is known to form FeHPO₄⁺ below pH 2.0. It is likely that the complex formed by Fe²⁺ ion with phosphoric acid will be similar (FeHPO₄) and the stability constant *K* can be obtained by

$$K = \frac{(\text{FeHPO}_4)}{(\text{Fe}^{2+}) \times f_{2+} (\text{HPO}_4^{2-}) f_{2-}} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

The concentration and the activity coefficients have been evaluated in the following way. The calculated values of the constant are recorded in Table I.

Phosphoric acid is present both as H₃PO₄ and H₂PO₄⁻ (the concentrations of HPO₄²⁻ and PO₄³⁻ are relatively small at the pH range used). The reaction with Fe²⁺ ions may be represented as

Now, if 'r' is the ratio of (H₃PO₄):(H₂PO₄⁻) and the total concentration of phosphoric acid is 'T' molar, the concentration of (H₃PO₄) would be r/(r+1) T molar and (H₂PO₄⁻), T/(r+1) molar. According to reactions (2) and (3), T moles of phosphoric acid would liberate (2r+1)/(r+1) T moles of H⁺ ions when T moles of FeHPO₄ are formed. The concentration of H⁺ ions liberated is known from the difference in pH values of the solutions containing Fe(ClO₄)₂ and H₃PO₄ and the corresponding blank. The concentration of FeHPO₄ is obtained by dividing the concentration of hydrogen ion by (2r+1)/(r+1). Next we calculate (HPO₄²⁻). The total concentration of phosphoric acid in solution is given by

$$(\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4) + (\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^-) + (\text{HPO}_4^{2-}) + (\text{PO}_4^{3-}) + (\text{FeHPO}_4) = \text{total conc. of H}_3\text{PO}_4$$

or

$$a_{\text{HPO}_4^{2-}} = \frac{(\text{Phosphoric acid})_{\text{total}} - (\text{FeHPO}_4)}{(a_{\text{H}^+}^2/K_1K_2) + (a_{\text{H}^+}/K_2f_-) + 1/f_{2-} + K_3/a_{\text{H}^+}f_{3-}}$$

Thus from pH, total concentration of H₃PO₄, and concentration of (FeHPO₄), we can determine a_{HPO₄²⁻}. Because of the lack of knowledge of the ionic radius, the Debye-Hückel equation could not be used in calculating the activity coefficients of ions. Instead, an alternative empirical relationship:

$$-\log f_i = 0.5Z_i^2 \{ \mu^{1/2}/(1 + \mu^{1/2}) - C\mu \}$$

(where C=0.2, Z_i = the valency of the ion, and μ=ionic strength), suggested by Davies⁴, has been used.

4. J. Chem. Soc., 1938, 2093.

The agreement between the thermodynamic constants from the sets of measurements at two different ionic strengths justifies the use of the empirical Davies equation.

From the equilibrium constants at two different temperatures, ΔH and ΔS have been calculated, assuming ΔH to be constant over the range of temperature studied. The value of ΔH is 12.8 (± 2) kcal./mole and $\Delta S = 75(\pm 6)$ e. u.

HPO_4^{2-} may be regarded as a bidentate group. The formation of a four-membered chelate ring is possible in the case of Fe^{2+} ion having the structure:

similar to that suggested by Genge and Salmon⁵ for the trivalent metal ions. According to them, the optimum ionic radius of the metal ion should be about 0.7 Å to obtain a strain-free ring. The ionic radii⁶ of Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions are 0.76 Å and 0.64 Å respectively. This suggests that the chelate ring formation of Fe^{2+} ion with H_3PO_4 is possible, but the ring is likely to be strained due to greater ionic radius. Earlier qualitative reports and the present determination show that ferrous phosphate complex is far less stable compared to FeHPO_4^+ (cf. earlier reports; our results are in the process of being communicated).

As to the enthalpy and entropy changes associated with the formation of FeHPO_4 , the former is not favourable for the formation of complex, but the latter is. A comparison of our value with ΔS in literature is not possible as we do not find any for similar complexes. Incidentally, it will be of interest to calculate ΔS of formation of this complex and compare it with the experimental value. Applying the entropy cycle of Evans and Nancollas⁷, we get:

$$\Delta S_{\text{FeHPO}_4} \text{ in solution} = \Delta S_{\text{h}(\text{Fe}^{2+})} + \Delta S_{\text{h}(\text{HPO}_4^{2-})} + \Delta S_{\text{FeHPO}_4(\text{g})} - \Delta S_{\text{h}(\text{FeHPO}_4)}$$

Of the terms on the right hand side, ΔS of hydration of Fe^{2+} ion is known. $\Delta S_{\text{h}(\text{FeHPO}_4)}$ may be calculated on the basis of zero energy assumption or inert gas assumption⁸. The former provides $-\Delta S = 6.350$ e.u. and latter ≈ 20 e.u. The difficulty arises in estimating $\Delta S_{\text{h}(\text{HPO}_4^{2-})}$ and $\Delta S_{\text{FeHPO}_4(\text{g})}$. For the latter, one could possibly use a value of 20 e.u., following Austin *et al.*⁹, whereas the former calculated on the assumption that ΔS_{h} is proportional to $1/r$, thus affording a value of ≈ 60 e.u. ($r_{\text{HPO}_4^{2-}} = 4 \text{ \AA}$)¹⁰. Adding these, we get for ΔS , a range of ≈ 60 to 74 e.u., using the extreme values of $\Delta S_{\text{h}(\text{FeHPO}_4)}$ in fair agreement with the experimental value.

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